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D.8.3 Report on existing RI centralised procedures

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Abstract

This deliverable has been elaborated within IPERION HS Work Package (WP) 8 – Central support activities – that has been designed to mimic the activities of the future European Research Infrastructure for Heritage Science (E-RIHS) European Research Infrastructure Consortium (ERIC). In this WP, two of six tasks were dedicated to training T8.2 (Integrated access to training activities) and T8.3 (Communication). This deliverable examines how these activities are organized by other ERICs and within IPERION HS project. In this mapping exercise, the formal delivery of task 8.5, the information was collected through the analysis of the websites of ERICs, through questionnaires and in person interviews with training/communication officers at ERICs. Practical considerations regarding the communication and training support activities are summarized in view of establishing E-RIHS ERIC.

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Abbreviations

Abbreviations	Expansion
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
ERIC	European Research Infrastructure Consortium
ESFRI	European Strategy Forum on Research Infrastructures
HS	Heritage Science
CON	Communication Officers' Network
PCO	Partner Communication Officer
RI(s)	Research Infrastructure(s)

Narrative (technical) description

1 Introduction

This mapping exercise is organized in two sections 2.1 Communication and 2.2 Training strategies of RIs.

2 Core text

2.1 Communication strategies of research infrastructures

A Research Infrastructure (RI) is a virtual or real place where researchers can find services for their research. A RI is usually composed of a central hub and some national nodes. Many public organizations, research centers, universities, museums, international organizations, etc. are part of each national node. So many researchers and providers are part of the community.

For this reason, communication becomes a strategic issue. That's why it is important to understand how to manage the communication flow within a large consortium as well as what are the proper working tools a research infrastructure should consider. In the last few years, research infrastructures started thinking about these matters and other criticalities such as the catalogues of services, the marketplaces, the EOSC policies, the Monitoring System, etc. Although they came from different perspectives, they have been included in the ESFRI strategy and they are also a question of communication strategy.

Due to the establishing E-RIHS ERIC, learning from the experience of other consolidated research infrastructures is fundamental to avoid waste of effort and time. Two approaches have been used to compare the communication strategies currently adopted in other research infrastructures:

- Launch of a survey both by email to a limited number of communication officers of European Research Infrastructures and by Slack application within the community dedicated to the communication officers of the research infrastructures (Research Infrastructures Communicators: ri-comms.slack.com) worldwide.
- Gathering and analysis of information collected from the official websites of all the 489 research infrastructures included in the list of the RICH observatory: <http://observatory.rich2020.eu/rich/facilities/subview?q=489&t=ALL>

2.1.1 The IPERION HS survey on communication inside other RIs

Figure 1: Screenshot of the survey on communication

The construction of our survey is based on the experience of the RI-VIS project that launched a survey on Communication Tools in August 2020. The RI-VIS staff interviewed 20 managers of RIs distributed across the world. The results highlighted that:

- Face-to-face interactions are the best way to engage stakeholders
- Many RIs do not monitor communication activities and don't have set KPIs
- Many RIs do not have dedicated staff for research communications and when present, the staff is not sufficient
- Social and other media (web-based catalogue, newsletter, videos) are not considered so relevant, despite they play a relevant role mainly in communication with existing users.

The survey, launched by IPERION HS in 2022, addressed the RIs already established in Europe. It has been organized into 19 questions, the first 9 related to the RIs communication at the central level and the other 10 (Q11-19) to communication at the level of the national nodes. Only 8 out of many communication officers (15 personally contacted and 504 reached by message on Slack) answered the survey. The collected data are discussed in more detail below.

Table 1 List of the RIs engaged in the survey (data from 2022)

Name	Country Hub	Central	National nodes	Observers
Lifewatch ERIC	Spain		8	
CLARIN ERIC	Netherlands		22	3
EMSO ERIC	Italy		9	6
SIOS international organization (Svalbard Integrated Arctic Earth Observing System)	Norway		11	
CESSDA ERIC	Norway		23	

DARIAH ERIC	Germany (distributed)	20	1
EPOS ERIC	Italy	25	
EATRIS ERIC	Netherlands	14	

Figure 2 Domain of the RIs analysed

The data show, that most RIs have a communication office included in the Central Hub (90%) (Figure 3), while for instance in DARIAH ERIC, the communication office (and the coordination office) is decentralised in at least four locations (<https://www.dariah.eu/contact/>).

Figure 3 Outcomes collected for the question "Does the Communication Office exist at the central hub? Or is it part of a Central Office?"

Regarding the number of dedicated personnel, 45% RIs have only one communication officer, 33% have two and Lifewatch and CLARIN ERICs have three people devoted to communication. The personnel comprise trained experts with communication skills (88,9%), and in one case, communication is performed by scientists (Figures 4 and 5).

Figure 4 Outcomes collected for the question “How many people work as communication/outreach officers in your RI at the central level?”

Figure 5 Outcomes collected for the question “Are communication activities performed by skilled persons without specific skills?”

All the interviewed RIs use Twitter and LinkedIn as social media, 88.9% have a YouTube account, and 66.7% also use Facebook. SIOS has also an Instagram profile, while EPOS uses Flickr. (Figure 6)

Figure 6 Outcomes collected for the question “Which social media does your RI have?”

These results are in line with the [survey launched within the RI-VIS project](#).

Interestingly, three out of ten RIs have an annual budget dedicated to communication.

The answers (A11-19), related to communication of the national nodes, have been very informative. Four out of ten RIs have personnel (mainly scientists) performing communication activities but without any specific training. Only EMSO ERIC has personnel with trained communication skills also at level of the national nodes.

Usually, the communication between the central hub and the national nodes does not follow specific workflows. On the other hand, for example, EMSO ERIC has established a Communication Service Group that meets yearly to discuss the communication strategy, plan and verify its effectiveness. The communication officer at the central hub meets the communication officers of the national nodes regularly (about four meetings per year).

In general, the national nodes do not have their own websites or social media. Only EMSO has websites activated in several national nodes.

Suggestions coming from the communication officers highlight that communication is not easy task because of the lack of personnel and resources as well as of the huge number of activities to be supported (e.g. training, meetings with political and industrial stakeholders, research activities, internal communication, participation in other EU projects, etc.). A strong suggestion is to establish a Communications Group to gather communicators working in the national nodes and other partner institutions to exchange information in a structured manner.

2.1.2 *The analysis of communication of the RIs through the websites*

In March 2022, information on communication of other RIs was collected by examining their websites, as listed by the [RICH Observatory](#) (Table 2). Initially, 104 European RIs have been considered. After a first analysis, the list was reduced to the 44 RIs with two main characteristics: (1) the legal status of an already established RI (ERIC, AISBL, etc.) or being part of the H2020 programme, (2) an informative (and updated) website.

Table 2 Type of data collected

Type of organization (as defined in the websites)	Research infrastructure - ERIC - AISBL - GmbH - EIROforum - GANIL - RI project - Project Cluster - RI cluster - Non-profit organization - Community - Initiative - ESFRI PP - ESFRI step - ESFRI IP - ESFRI OP
Year	(Year in which the research infrastructure has been officially established)
Domain	Cross domain - Data, Computing and Digital RI, Energy - Environmental sciences - Health and food - Material sciences and Analytical facilities - Physical sciences and engineering - Social and cultural innovation
Name of the research infrastructure	(Acronym of the research infrastructure)
Coordinator country	(Acronym of the coordinator country)
Number of national nodes + observers/partners/RIs	(This number is to compare communication proportionally)

Number of observers	(Just to verify the potentiality and impact of the research infrastructure)
Countries involved	(To define the scale of the research infrastructure)
Offices related to coordination and communications (and how they are named)	Central Office - Coordination Office - Outreach Office - Work Package or Task (in case of a project) - None
Communication Staff	Number of people officially appointed
Website of the infrastructure	(It has been noted also if the website was updated or not)
Social media	None - Facebook - Twitter - LinkedIn - Instagram - Youtube - Flickr - a combination of the above mentioned

European RIs in all domains seem to have the following similar features:

- In many cases, the communication staff is part of the coordination/central office
- Most ERICs have one person in charge of communication
- The only RI with four persons in communication is ICOS, working in the energy field.
- When the communication staff is appointed and has specific skills, the RI has more than one social medium account. When communication is performed by scientists, the RI has only one social media account, preferably Twitter.

The most used social media are Twitter (31,5%), LinkedIn (21,8%) and YouTube (18,5%). (Figures 7 and 8)

Figure 7: Communication staff (number of employees)

Figure 8 Social media accounts used in the RIs (%)

In the Social and Cultural Innovation domain, in which the current IPERION HS and E-RIHS IP projects and the future E-RIHS ERIC belong, the analysis considered six RIs: five ERICs (SHARE, DARIAH, CLARIN, CESSDA, ESS) and one AISBL (OPERAS). All the RIs have more than 15 national nodes, so they are comparable with current E-RIHS dimension. Five out of six have a central/coordination office with only one communication officer. All six RIs have at least two or more social media accounts, mainly Twitter, LinkedIn and YouTube. None of them uses Instagram.

2.1.3 The experience of the Heritage Science community of IPERION HS

Starting from IPERION CH (H2020 GA 654028), the community has invested in building a model for communication inside the large consortium that comprised 24 partners. Deliverable D11.4 (*IPERION CH Communication Plan*) describes the procedure of appointing a “Partner Communication Officer” (PCO) and a deputy PCO in each institution participating in IPERION CH, with the responsibilities for internal communication inside their institution and with the partner’s third parties.

The duties of the PCOs were **defined** as follows (D11.4, p.12):

- Deliver messages received from the Coordination Office (CO) to the relevant recipients in their institutions
- Collect and prepare material for communication from the researchers of their institutions
- Send relevant news to the CO and the Editorial Committee for inclusion on the website, social media and other communication tools.

In the E-RIHS PP (H2020 project, GA n.739503), thanks to the nature of the project, the external communication was performed jointly with IPERION CH that focused on research activities and transnational access. Both projects ran in parallel and closed in 2019. The specific E-RIHS PP communication was focused mainly on internal communication among partners and towards the political stakeholders. With these premises, some relevant ideas around communication were developed as described in D10.3 “Report on the implementation and evaluation of communication”:

- Logo as a trademark – In 2019 the E-RIHS logo was registered as a trademark in Europe, Canada, USA, Brasil, Peru, and Argentina.

- Visual identity and digital communication toolkit – To reinforce the trademark's value, the communication office created the E-RIHS visual identity, guidelines that describe how to communicate E-RIHS in a consistent way with the aim of reinforcing the E-RIHS identity and reputation. Using the same design and style at central and national levels guarantees effective and immediate recognition from the audience. The guidelines contain instructions on the use of the logo, the colour palette, the typography, the creation of the logo of the national nodes, the creation of communication materials and at last the design of the websites of the national nodes. The visual identity was annexed to the deliverable “E-RIHS PP Dissemination and Communication strategy”.
- Website’s template – an IT package with the template of the official E-RIHS website (based on WordPress) was distributed among the national nodes. This way, each national node received the basis to build and personalise its website with respect to a few, essential instructions. The experiment went quite well, depending on the country. In view of the establishment of the E-RIHS ERIC, the E-RIHS website and the equivalent template are going to be renewed. On the occasion, respect for the rules/instructions in the use of the logo and website will be strongly recommended.
- Heritage Science Hub – The Heritage Science Hub (HSH) is a semantic tool created to aggregate information on research news, publications, job opportunities, training opportunities, etc. in the field of heritage science. The system allows the users to save personal research and have it automatically updated. Its functionalities are fully described in the D10.2 E-RIHS Heritage Hub online however it an extra budget is needed before the final release.

Building on experience of past projects, the idea of the communication officers’ network (CON) was further developed in IPERION HS. The CON was appointed at the kick-off meeting in April 2020, meets at least twice per year and participates in general project meetings.

The role of the CON has been defined as follows:

1. amplifying the IPERION HS messages (news, videos, photos, etc...) inside the community of the national node, through their website, national social media, etc... in some cases, the information could be translated into the national language
2. collecting information (photos, videos, posts, articles, etc...) related to the national node and share with the central communication office to make IPERION HS communication consistent and relevant for the whole heritage science community (newsletter, social media, etc...)
3. promoting the transnational access offer inside his/her own country
4. developing a communication strategy and drafting the D8.1 IPERION HS Communication Plan, partially based on the recommendations in the RI-VIS toolkit.

The CON decided to use the following tools:

- Email - to exchange official information
- Messenger - to quickly share news and posts

- An online doc named “Communication Officers’ logbook” - to list events and activities to do and carried out, to share hashtags and accounts, etc..

The communication flow among researchers, single institutions/facilities, national nodes, and the Central Office is circular and can be summarised as follows:

- (1) researchers share relevant scientific outputs (research results, publications, collaboration, etc.) with their institution that passes the news to the national node.
- (2) for the news of national relevance, the national node publishes the news on its website and social media and asks the Central Office to repost it.
- (3) for the news of international relevance, the national node has a double opportunity: it can either publish the news on its website and social media and asks the Central Office to repost it or ask the Central Office to post the news on the main website and social media and then repost it on the national channels.

In the transition phase towards the ERIC, IPERION HS has been sharing a common strategy with E-RIHS to allow people to immediately recognize the community and interact with it.

2.2 Organization of training activities at existing RIs

From November 2022 to February 2023, IPERION HS collected information on how training activities are organized in other research infrastructures (RIs). Data were collected by:

- browsing their websites
- collecting responses through a survey form (Annex 3)
- taking interviews with their staff.

2.2.1 The analysis of training activities of the RIs through the websites

The legally established RIs or those being part of the H2020 programme were considered for the first mapping exercise. The data were collected for 36 RIs. Table 3 reports the type of information collected and analyzed per each RI.

Table 3 – Data collected from each RI related to training activities

Type of organization (as defined in the websites)	Research infrastructure - ERIC - AISBL - GmbH - Forum EIROfoum - GANIL - RI project - Project Cluster - RI cluster - Non-profit organization - Community - Initiative - ESFRI PP - ESFRI step - ESFRI IP - ESFRI OP
Year	When the research infrastructure has been officially established
Domain	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Cross domain - Data, Computing and Digital - Energy

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Environmental sciences - Health and food - Material sciences and Analytical facilities - Physical sciences and engineering - Social and cultural innovation
Name (full list)	RICH; EUDAT; OpenAIRE; GÉANT; PRACE; ICOS; Euro-Argo; EPOS; LifeWatch; EMSO; EMBRC; Corbel; Infrafrontier; EATRIS; Instruct; Euro-Bioimaging; BBMRI-ERIC; OpenScreen; ECRIN; ELIXIR; Laserlab Europe; CERIC; CTA; European Spallation Source; Eli; ILL; ELT; CERN; ESFR EBS; EMFL; DARIAH; CLARIN; CESSDA; OPERAS; EOSC; SSHOC; DISSCO.
Training platform	if available, how the training is presented and organized on the RI website: training platform - training section on the main website - separate webpage - events in agenda etc.
Training services and related audience	If offered by the RI: workshops - summer schools - webinars - online training modules; Targeted at: educators - learners; researchers - PhD students - university students - school students - kids - wide audience etc.
Staff exchange / internships	if available, details
Aggregators registry	if available, details

The websites of the listed RIs contain the following information:

- Most of the analyzed RIs currently offer at least one or more types of training activities (92%, or 34 of 36 analyzed RIs). (Figure 9)
- More than half of the analyzed RIs (58%, 21 of 36) contain a dedicated section/webpage or an online platform of training activities. In 36% of the total (13 of 36), the online training platform requires users to register and log in to access services. At the same time, 42% of these RI websites currently do not contain a web space specifically dedicated to “training” or “education”. 8% out of 42% do not provide own training activities; while the remaining 34% inform the audience about offered training opportunities in the events/news or in other sections of the website.
- The analyzed European RIs offer different types of training activities: online webinars (64%), workshops (50%), online training modules (44%) and seasonal (summer/winter) schools (33%). 28% of their websites contain a registry/aggregator, e.g. courses, research repositories etc. (Figure 8)
- The dedicated webpages on training activities (not a stand-alone platform) are structured as follows:
 - In many cases, they do not classify training activities based on target audience. In most cases, this kind of information is provided per single event
 - Only the online training modules are targeted: for educators and for learners

- They include a search option per simple text search or keywords
- They have a contact form or an email to submit enquires to the training officer or the helpdesk service
- They include a news section to inform about training events, not only organized by the RI itself but also by external partners
- Few of them (16% of the total) give information on staff exchange and internship opportunities.

Figure 9: The graphs show the training activities, organized by RIs, according to the information available on their websites

2.2.2 IPERION HS survey on training activities at other ERICs

Following the results of the first mapping through the web, the more detailed and direct analysis considered 13 RIs, chosen based on their training offer, dimension, geographic coverage and scientific domain. All the RIs are already established and are comparable with the future E-RIHS structure for different reasons. The selected RIs are listed in Table 4.

Table 4 – RIs considered for training actives mapping

	Name	Central hub	National nodes	Observers	Domain	Training activities offered
1	CERIC		8		Environmental Sciences, Health and Food, Material Sciences and Analytical Facilities, Physical Sciences and Engineering, Energy	Webinars, workshops, summer/ winter schools

2	CESSDA	Norway	22	1	Social and cultural innovation	webinars, workshops, preparing guides (as Data management expert guide; Data archiving guide)
3	CLARIN	Netherlands	22	3	Social and cultural innovation	webinars, workshops, online training modules, Digital Humanities summer school; Moodle course on repositories produced in the context of an Erasmus+ project; registry of University courses
4	CTA				Physical sciences and engineering	Webinars, online training modules
5	DARIAH	Germany	20	1	Social and cultural innovation	workshops, summer/winter schools, webinars, online training modules, registry of University courses
6	EMBRC				Environmental sciences	workshops, online training modules, registry of University courses
7	EMSO	Italy	9	6	Environmental sciences	webinars, online training modules
8	ESFR-EBS				Physical sciences and engineering	Webinars, workshops, summer/winter schools, online training modules, staff exchange/internships
9	EURO BIOIMAGING	Finland	14		Health and food	Webinars, workshops, online training modules
10	LASERLAB	Germany	18		Material sciences and analytical facilities	Webinars
11	LIFEWATCH	Spain	8		Environmental sciences	Webinars, workshops
12	PRACE	Belgium	25	2	Data, computing and digital	Webinars, workshops, online training modules

For these RIs, IPERION HS developed a specific questionnaire (Figure 9) regarding the training strategy development, organization, implementation, and evaluation of training activities, as well as the involvement of the RIs in university education and the implementation of open science principles for training materials. The survey, disseminated among 13 selected RIs (through email and the [community of practice for training officers](#) (OpenAIRE)), included twenty questions (see Annex 2),

Q1-3: general information about the RI

Q4-11: staff and training strategy

Q12-15: involvement in university education (PhD programs etc.)

Q16-19: accessibility and evaluation of training activities

Q20: additional comments

obtaining responses from CLARIN, DARIAH, CESSDA, LifeWatch, CERIC and EMSO ERICs.

Based on survey responses, the training staff of CLARIN, CESSDA, EMSO, CERIC ERICs was invited for a short interview, for further clarifications/details and eventual comments/suggestions.

Figure 10: The IPERION HS survey on training activities at the RIs

The data from the survey analysis can be summarized as follows:

1. Organization and budget at the central level (Q5-6)

All the RIs organize training activities as an in-kind contribution at both levels: central hub and national nodes. 67% of RIs have a budget allocated specifically for training activities by the central hub, while 33% do not have it.

2. Training staff (Q7-8)

Half of the RIs (50%) have a dedicated staff working on training activities. If a training office is available, it is composed predominantly of one to three members, working full or part-time. (Figure 11)

Q7: Does the central hub of your research infrastructure have a dedicated staff/office working on training activities?

Q8: How many people are involved in organization of training activities at the central level?

Figure 11: The graphs illustrate the availability of dedicated training staff within the RIs and, the number of personnel involved in training at the central level.

3. Training offer (Q9)

All the RIs have included webinars and workshops in their training offer. 67% of the RIs also offer seasonal schools and online training modules. Furthermore, RIs provide other types of training activities (50%), depending on the scientific domain, like tutorials and scientific games (environmental sciences, e.g. LIFEWATCH-ERIC), a University Moodle course (social innovation, e.g. CLARIN-ERIC), guidelines (social innovation, e.g. CESSDA-ERIC) etc.

4. Training strategy (Q10-11)

Mainly, RIs have already developed a training strategy or are currently at the stage of its development. The strategy is revised differently: yearly or every 2, 3 or 4 years. The Director General, Board of Directors, Deputy Director or Executive Deputy Director are responsible for the development/upgrade of the training strategy, supported by the training officer (if available). Also, the roles of Knowledge Infrastructure and User Involvement Committees can give input on the training strategy.

5. University education (Q12-15)

Only a few of the RIs are involved in the delivery of formal University courses: 33% responded yes, while 67% no (or not yet). The two RIs that deliver University courses (CLARIN-ERIC and DARIAH-ERIC) have a strategic plan to develop more links with the University. None of the RIs currently have a specific request procedure for PhD students, while only 1 of 6 RIs (17%) provides funds for PhD studentships.

Q9: What kind of training activities does your research infrastructure offer?

Q12: Is your research infrastructure involved in the delivery of formal university training courses, e.g. by providing access to research facilities for the purpose of delivering university courses?

Figure 12: The graphs illustrate the training offer and the involvement of RIs in the delivery of formal University courses.

6. Website, contact and support (Q16-17)

83% of the examined RIs hosts a dedicated web space either a section, separate website or a standalone training platform.

The same number of RIs highlighted the importance of a dedicated helpdesk or email contact for training enquires. The role of this contact is strategic for gathering user feedback, suggestion, and consequently improving the products offered; for communicating with partners, editing and sourcing of training materials etc.

7. KPIs and monitoring (Q18-19)

The numbers of events, as well as participants in the events, organized by RIs vary significantly. The events usually count 20-30 participants, with higher numbers, e.g. 120 per event, for online activities. The majority of RIs have already adopted KPIs to monitor training activities, based on monitoring the number of participants per event; visualizations of online modules and feedbacks from a post-survey.

8. Additional comments (Q20)

The interviewees recommended discussing in-kind contribution at the beginning, considering the limitations of the available budget, as well as considering collaborations and services offered by other RIs. Training activities can be complex and challenging. Professional full-time staff is paramount for successful implementation.

2.2.3 ***Experience in organizing training activities at ERICs: interviews with ERIC training officers***

Interviews were held with the dedicated training staff at CLARIN and CESSDA and some clarifications were provided by EMSO and CERIC ERICs as follows:

- Internal staff training

CLARIN, CESSDA and EMSO ERICs highlighted the importance of organizing training for internal staff.

CLARIN-ERIC: the internal staff is supposed to attend the modules of the “Executive Masters in Management of Research Infrastructures (for more details, please visit: <https://emmri.unimib.it/>), offered online and on-site at the University in Milan, Italy. It recommends exploiting the materials produced by the ENRIITC (the European Network of Research Infrastructures and Industry for Collaboration) project, funded by the European Commission (for more details, please visit: <https://enriitc.eu/>), for internal staff training.

CESSDA-ERIC: training activities are strongly linked to widening and staff exchange activities. Yearly, CESSDA plans one or two training that is focused on staff from Service providers working in data repositories (on processes of archiving in SS data archives) that are open for everyone to attend. The CESSDA training working group is also finalising the “Data Archiving Guide” (for more details, please visit: <https://dag.cessda.eu/>) that will serve as a self-learning guide for future staff. There are specific meetings for technical staff (one of the topics is The Dataverse Project - Dataverse.org), mentorship and secondments to CESSDA partners as well as widening events: Widening and Outreach (cessda.eu).

EMSO-ERIC offers onboarding programs for new employees, as well as monthly training activities for CMO staff on marine techniques or methodologies with external experts.

- Training strategy and risks mitigation

IPERION HS interviewed both CLARIN-ERIC and CESSDA-ERIC on this topic. They plan their training activities in advance, also emphasizing their flexibility.

CESSDA-ERIC mitigates the risks of non-compliance with the plan of training activities by the way in which they organize these activities. The procedure can be described briefly as follows:

- 1) the number of training activities, the topics, as well as the assigned budget are planned in advance
- 2) the internal call for proposals among CESSDA Service Providers is opened
- 3) The CESSDA Service Providers submit the proposals with the PM cost estimation
- 4) The working group evaluates the proposals and selects the training activities to carry out.

Sometimes the members of the CESSDA Training Working Group (3-4) belong to Service providers. The costs of PM rate of Service providers may differ geographically. Topics, expertise

and budget can influence the decisions. The strong points of such an approach are not only the planning but flexibility as well.

- Funding for training activities

CLARIN and CESSDA-ERICs, interviewed on this subject, cover the expenses connected with training activities in two different ways.

CLARIN-ERIC has no dedicated funding, training activities are covered by the funds for the user involvement events: <https://www.clarin.eu/content/user-involvement-funding>. A permanent call for applications procedure selects the training activities, that include summer schools, workshops, online training modules.

CESSDA and EMSO have a dedicated budget for organizing training activities at central level. In case of CESSDA-ERIC, the training management varies according to the yearly plan (50.000-200.000 EUR).

- Organization and roles of training staff

EMSO-ERIC and CERIC-ERIC do not have personnel for organizing training activities. CLARIN-ERIC has dedicated training personnel at central level, while in Norway CESSDA-ERIC central office is dealing with only administration and project support, assigning organization of training activities to the dedicated training working group composed by the staff of service providers.

CESSDA-ERIC has four pillars, represented by working groups (WG), Training, Trust Seal, Tools, and Widening. The last three might require support by the training pillar (or training WG), when delivering and organizing events. Each pillar has a leader who sets up a small working group that deals with policy decisions and supports a few tasks implementation. All working group leads assigned deliver their work for few PM per year and are not employees of CESSDA Main office. The Training working group's leader is in Slovenia (Head of Department Social Sciences Data Archive, University of Ljubljana). Other members (3) of this working group work for CESSDA Service Providers are distributed across Europe. Members of Training WG meet monthly. Training working group members are the staff of CESSDA Service providers that have legal obligations by signing a dedicated contract (0.5PM/year). The budget gives additional responsibilities. The composition of the working group is mainly stable (the same for the last three years). The person continues being part of the working group if requested. It assures constant expertise in the field and consistent planning of internal staff training. At the same time, flexibility and internal staff training are essential for unavoidable temporary or long-term changes (retirement, maternity leave etc.). CESSDA internal calls select the working groups' members. However, the training working group leader is involved not only in training but also in different activities, including communication and design of different tools.

- Open access training materials

CLARIN-ERIC and CESSDA-ERIC are trying to make training materials available as open as possible, while EMSO-ERIC does not have open access policy for training materials yet.

The teaching materials on the CLARIN page are freely accessible, even if some of them are deposited on Zenodo with restricted access due to constraints imposed by the university of the teacher who developed those materials.

CESSDA created the "Training resources" catalogue last year (<https://www.cessda.eu/Training-Resources>) to provide free training materials. The CESSDA training working group is currently finalizing events checklist (i.e. instructions for internal and external staff on how to carry out training activities, including practical and technical issues) that will be available in open access.

- University education

CESSDA-ERIC is not formally involved in delivering University courses, while EMSO-ERIC is actively planning this involvement. CLARIN-ERIC is actively involved in the University education. Soon they will publish a Moodle course on repositories produced in the context of an Erasmus+ project. Each year, CLARIN-ERIC co-funds the Digital Humanities summer school. In addition, CLARIN-ERIC and DARIAH-ERIC developed a joint registry of Digital Humanities University courses: <https://dhcr.clarin-dariah.eu>.

- PhD education

Among RIs that participated in the survey, only CERIC-ERIC is formally offering PhD studentships and CLARIN-ERIC has some plans for future in this direction. The Deputy Executive Director of CERIC-ERIC provided detailed answers to the questions Q14-15.

Q14: Does your research infrastructure have a specific access request procedure for PhD students? No

Access to CERIC facilities does not currently follow any criterion that grants priority. In the past, CERIC ERIC developed a specific programme to improve their use from Balkan countries or Eastern countries without large RIs, but once the programme ended, the only criteria applied was the quality of the proposal and no more the provenance or career status of the applicant. The reason is that some facilities provide to CERIC only 10% of their access time, this means they carry out one or two proposals per semester with an instrument, too short to prioritise access (prioritising one would mean excluding the others).

Q15: Does your research infrastructure provide funding for PhD studentships? Yes.

CERIC-ERIC opened a call for 20 PhD positions in 2020 (for more details, please visit: <https://www.ceric-eric.eu/2020/10/06/phd-opportunities/>), distributed across life sciences, research on batteries and other topics of partner facilities (analogous to national nodes). CERIC ERIC invited the partner facilities to submit the topics, a short description of the programme, and a budget required. One tutor had to belong to the facility, a second one to a university. PhD students should spend time in other facilities (the PhD programme must involve at least 2 CERIC ERIC partner facilities PFs) and report the activities to the scientific advisory committee annually. Recently, a new call was opened, not specific for PhDs but for other type of investment, including PhDs and postdocs, with similar conditions to the previous but without any indication on the topics. CERIC ERIC also will activate over twelve positions between PhDs, postdocs and technicians. The universities issue the PhD, while CERIC ERIC hosts the students at the facilities.

2.2.4 *The experience of the Heritage Science community at IPERION HS*

In the last decades, and in particular during IPERION CH (2015-2019, H2020 GA 654028), the community planned and delivered training activities. The consortium offered mainly on-site training camps and doctoral summer schools in heritage science and fostering interest in TransNational Access (TNA).

Within the IPERION HS project, dedicated Work Package (Training and Engagement) planned and organized, with the support of WP8, the training activities, under an umbrella label HS Academy. This covers a wide range of cutting-edge training opportunities in Heritage Science. The establishment of the HS Academy represents a relevant achievement in engaging with users and potential users, on one side, and with the RI providers, on the other side.

In the training offered, HS Academy has two main objectives:

- Inform potential users of TNA services about the available scientific instruments in IPERION HS
- provide training on specific subjects of interest to the Heritage Science community. The experience of organizing training events, collecting and making available training materials in open access, is essential for the training activities of the future E-RIHS community.

The IPERION HS project develops and organizes both experimented and new training formats:

1. Doctoral Summer Schools;
2. On-site Training Camps;
3. HS Academy webinars;
4. HS Academy lectures;
5. Online training modules.

The dedicated staff, under a specific task (T8.2 Integrated access two training activities), has ensured a single-entry point to all training events. This allowed better user experience, having all the information gathered, updated and distributed centrally. The dedicated person in central office is in charge of responding to all the queries related to training addressed to the central office. This training officer is in charge of preparing the registration form for the applicants, collecting the relevant information from the partners, drafting promotional materials and making sure they comply with project visual identity, publishing regular announcements on social media and website. The training officer is in charge of collecting satisfactory feedback from the participants in the training events and elaborating the relative Key Performance Indicators. This feedback is delivered to the Quality officer, project coordinator and the Work Package leaders for the evaluation and implementation of improvements.

- Doctoral Summer schools

Differently from those organized previously within the IPERION CH project, the 1st IPERION HS Doctoral Summer School on “Excellence in Heritage Science for conservation and collection care research and access” (July 2021) was organized online due to COVID-19 pandemic regulations in force. The online modality allowed increasing the number of active participants significantly (from 20 to 190). The 2nd IPERION HS Doctoral Summer School “Environmental impact on built heritage and its digitalisation” will be held in presence at ZAG (Slovenian National Building and Civil Engineering Institute), in Ljubljana, Slovenia. Following the success of the previous online edition, a new hybrid form for lectures (not for practical activities) will be used to offer training to a wider audience.

- On-site training camps

Following the experience of IPERION CH Training Camps, the IPERION HS Training Camps offer a hands-on experience on the functioning of the MOLAB and FIXLAB platforms, which give access to an impressive collection of advanced analytical instrumentation for non-invasive measurements on precious, fragile or immovable objects, archaeological sites and historical monuments. A small community of researchers hosts on-site training camps (HS-TCs) in locations where access to advanced knowledge in science and technology for CH is under-represented. The HS Academy TCs comprise at least five intensive days of lectures, hands-on experience, and lab and group projects. HS Academy offers training camps on possibly different and relevant topics for heritage science. For

instance, the 1st HS Academy Training Camp was held on “A hands-on experience to learn FIXLAB techniques applied to paleontological and paleoanthropological heritage”. It was held at the National Centre on Human Evolution in Burgos and at Atapuerca UNESCO fossil sites (Spain) in July 2022). The 2nd HS Academy Training camp will be focussed on “Built heritage in changing environment” and be held at ITAM (Institute of Theoretical and Applied Mechanics) in Telč, Czech Republic.

- HS Academy webinars

Webinars are a key-source of state-of-the-art information on Heritage Science research, facilities, policy and impact. The series contributes to develop a vibrant heritage science community and is for anyone involved in interdisciplinary heritage science research. In 2021 and 2022, HS Academy held ten webinars. The audience grew time by time by engaging people from many countries worldwide. Satisfaction surveys were submitted after each event, audience appreciated the webinars generally and expressed a positive sentiment.

- HS Academy lectures

Starting from September 2022, HS Academy launched a new online training opportunity called “Current Topics in Heritage Science” lecture series. The organizers, a team of young researchers and emerging professionals inside the consortium, planned ten lectures to be delivered in 2022 and 2023. This new format provides free online training on fundamental knowledge about techniques and methodologies, as well as on specific heritage typologies and other topics of interest to the heritage science field. The lectures are targeted at emerging professionals, such as students and young researchers, as well as to advanced conservators, curators, restorers, and other cultural heritage stakeholders, covering university, public and private sectors. Attendance is free, and the lectures are typically 30 min long, followed by a Q&A session. Video recordings of the lectures are uploaded on the E-RIHS YouTube channel. Satisfaction surveys were submitted after each event and confirm that the audience appreciates the format.

- HS Academy Training activities on the IPERION HS website

Training activities and online modules are uploaded and promoted on the IPERION HS website in the HS Academy section, the user can find news about the upcoming events and register, and consult separate webpages dedicated to each training event.

2.3 What can be learnt from the other RIs

It is not easy to propose a model for communication and training inside a RI of medium or large size. There are many variables that need to be considered. Anyway, some suggestions come from the experience of the RIs already established and from the past experiences of the heritage science community.

2.3.1 Communication

The results of the first mapping of other RIs websites related to communication highlighted that:

- At the central level, **communication staff is usually included in the coordination office**. The activities are strictly correlated with those of outreach, training, access, etc. So, it can be useful to be part of the same structure and have a shared planning of the activities.

- It would be advisable to **allocate an annual budget** to organize and plan communication in a proper way. The lack of resources does not contribute to have a coherent and consistent strategy. Another suggestion is to participate in European calls to ensure a certain sustainability of communication activities.
- A **carefully structured communication plan** contributes to defining it, ensuring timely and effective communications, choosing the proper tone of voice, and setting up the activities to reach different audiences (e.g. scientific community, industrial environment, policy-making environment, media, citizens, RI staff, etc.). It is crucial to invite the stakeholders to participate in the life of the RI. Using different languages for different stakeholders is a strategic choice.
- The **creation of a visual identity** guarantees recognizable and consistent communication inside and outside the community, while the opportunity to register the logo as a trademark protects it. It is useful to share a digital communication toolkit composed of templates for presentations, letterhead, brochures and flyers, digital cards, gadgets, etc. The instruction for the use of the communication materials should be explained in the visual identity guidelines. It could be useful also to prepare communication materials for events and a to-do list to check whether their organization is in line with the communication strategy and the visual identity.
- At the national level, the **creation of a network of communication officers** helps with information exchange, even if this also depends on who oversees this activity. Many RIs have skilled people inside the central office but they do not have experts and expertise inside the national nodes. Some RIs highlighted the lack of personnel as a limit in performing communication at the central and national levels. It would be helpful to engage and train researchers in communication and provide them with the tools to carry out communication and its monitoring at the national level.
- **Periodic meetings** are necessary to plan a shared communication strategy, monitor activities, discuss criticalities and improvements, propose joint initiatives, etc. Face-to-face interactions are preferable, and they are the most fruitful occasions to work on common objectives and to reinforce personal relations inside the consortium. It is also important to create a digital environment to share news in real-time by using chat tools (like Messenger, Telegram, etc.) and participate in the Slack community of communication officers to exchange experiences, present doubts, plan joint initiatives, etc. Creating an internal forum for discussion inside the single RI is an additional, valuable tool.
- Each RI can decide **to set up a website at the central level** or can evaluate the opportunity to create a template of the website to be shared with the national nodes, so they can have their websites. They should not be a duplicate of the central website but represent an opportunity to engage the national communities and the public at large in their native language. The national websites can be organized in a personalized way.
- **Social media** can reach thousands of people. RIs should have a social media strategy, identify hashtags, and boost them. RIs mainly use Twitter, LinkedIn, and YouTube. Some RIs should consider also opening an Instagram account. Visuals (images and videos) have a large impact

on the young generation and their engagement. In this moment (2023), it would be appropriate to make a more in-depth reflection and evaluate the opportunity to move Twitter accounts into Mastodon, a new social media structured on more ethical principles.

- **Monitoring the website and social media of the RIs** gives a huge amount of information on how to improve the communication strategy and grow the social impact. Communication must reach the public at large-scale to make RIs more understandable and to explain how public funding is spent. In 2019 the ESFRI Working Group on monitoring RIs performance released a report proposing a set of KPIs for pan-European RIs. All the RIs communication officers should use these standardized indicators in order to compare data among RIs. It would be also useful to plan an annual workshop/roundtable for RIs communication officers to share best practices and discuss criticalities.

Communication is strategic to make RIs truly impactful!

2.3.2 *Training*

The results of the first mapping of other RIs websites related to training highlighted that:

- A distinguishable and updated **web space dedicated to training activities** is essential (website, platform etc.)
- **Targeted training opportunities** are crucial to reach the appropriate audience. It is crucial to tag information with type of training, date, time, organizer and place and give a structured description of the event
- Helpdesk or email contact of a training office on the website is an added value.

The survey and interviews with the RIs team highlighted that:

- Availability of **funding for organization of training activities** at central level is fundamental
- **Dedicated training staff**, as well as generally competences of the personnel responsible for central activities, are essential; for this reason, it is necessary to provide internal training to the staff
- Many RIs consider it a priority to be involved in **university education**, and the E-RIHS community should consider it critical. Although not generally implemented by RIs yet but recommended by the most recent European policies, involvement in PhD education can be a crucial direction for the E-RIHS agenda and strategy
- In the social innovation domain, RIs (e.g. CLARIN, CESSDA) dedicate particular effort to develop **online training modules and data repositories**. Their experience is relevant to the future E-RIHS-ERIC, including social and humanities disciplines, and underlines the high value of open access to digital archives
- In the environmental sciences domain RIs show efforts in **offering training activities to the private sector**, strengthening the link between research and industry. In addition, they also implement unusual types of specific training activities (e.g. scientific games, tracking and monitoring tools). Their example can inspire the future E-RIHS ERIC

- ESFRI recommends **practicing Open Science**. Since the beginning, E-RIHS ERIC should define an Open Science policy and follow the best practices in Open Access also for training
- E-RIHS ERIC should also strengthen the collaboration and exchange of experiences with other RIs, and EOSC.

To develop and implement a successful training strategy, the appropriate agreements and clear rules should be made between the ERIC central hub and the national nodes, as well as an appropriate budget should be allocated (including in-kind contribution), according to the type and number of activities, train the internal staff, practice open science and create a network with other RIs and the academy.

3 Annexes

3.1 Annex 1: Survey on communication inside research infrastructures

Title: Communication inside your research infrastructure. How to plan an effective communication strategy

I am Laura Benassi, the communication officer at IPERION HS, a European project (H2020-INFRAIA-2019-1, GA 871034) that contributes to establishing E-RIHS ERIC, the European Research Infrastructure for Heritage Science (E-RIHS, <http://www.e-rihs.eu/>). I kindly ask you to share your experience as a communication officer of research infrastructure and give me suggestions to set up an efficient communication strategy inside my community. I am grateful to those who will help me.

- Q1 What is the name of your research infrastructure?
- Q2 Where is the central hub located (country, city)?
- Q3 How many national nodes does your research infrastructure have?
- Q4 Does a Communication Office exist at the central hub? Or is it part of a Central Office?
 Yes, it exists as a stand-alone office
 Yes, it exists but it is part of the Central Hub
 No, it doesn't exist
 Comments
- Q5 How many people work as communication/outreach officers in your research infrastructure at the central level?
 0
 1
 3 or more
- Q6 Are the communication activities performed by skilled persons and researchers without specific skills?
 Communication is performed by people with skills in communication
 Communication is performed by researchers without specific skills in communication
 Comments
- Q7 Which social media does your research infrastructure have?
 Facebook
 Twitter
 LinkedIn
 Instagram
 YouTube
 My research infrastructure doesn't use any social media
 Other (please specify)
- Q8 Which budget does the research infrastructure have for communication and outreach activities yearly (expressed in €)?
- Q9 Does each national node have a communication officer or working in communication?
- Q10 If yes, how many people work in communication in each national node?
- Q11 How is communication organized at the central node? And in each national node?
- Q12 What is the communication workflow between the central hub and the national nodes? How does the central hub manage communication with the national node? and vice versa?

- Q13 If the national nodes have a communication officer, does the central hub meet regularly with them?
Yes
No
It depends on the communication activities to be carried out
Other (please specify)
- Q14 How many times do you meet per year?
- Q15 Which tool/s does the central hub use to manage communication with the national nodes?
Email
Website
Project management tools (Basecamp, Wiki, D4science, etc.)
Newsletter
Videoconference meeting
In presence meeting
Other (please specify)
- Q16 Does each national node have its own website?
Yes
No
Other (please specify)
- Q17 Does each national node have its own social media?
Yes
No
Other (please specify)
- Q18 As a communication officer of research infrastructure, have you any useful suggestions or comments to share with me?
- Q19 Is there anything else you'd like to share about your experience?

3.2 Annex 2: Survey on how training activities are organized inside research infrastructures

Title: Training activities at your ERIC

Text email:

Dear [name] [surname],

we contact you on behalf of IPERION HS (www.iperionhs.eu), a European project that contributes to establishing E-RIHS ERIC, the research infrastructure for heritage science.

We are currently working on the design of the training strategy of the future ERIC.

We would like to collect the best practices already existing in the ERICs, for this reason we selected your infrastructure for an interview. We would kindly ask you to distribute the following survey (8-minutes-questionnaire) among your internal ERIC staff directly involved in the organization of training activities:

<https://www.surveymonkey.com/r/5827R6P>

Furthermore, we were wondering if you could indicate the name of the person responsible for training activities at your ERIC, whom we could contact for a short Zoom interview.

We appreciate your time and valuable contribution to this mission. We remain at your disposal for any further information.

Best regards,

IPERION HS team

Survey form questions:

Q1 What is the name of your research infrastructure?

Q2 Where is the central hub located (country, city)?

Q3 How many national nodes does your research infrastructure have?

Q4 Does your research infrastructure organize training activities?

Q5 Are training activities provided as part of the in-kind contributions from the national nodes or organized by the central hub?

Other (please specify):

Q6 In case they are organized by the central hub, does it have a budget for these activities?

If yes, specify in euros (yearly):

Q7 Does the central hub of your research infrastructure have a dedicated staff/office working on training activities?

Comments

Q8 How many people are involved in organization of training activities at the central level?

0

1-3

More than 3

- Q9 What kind of training activities does your research infrastructure offer?
- Workshops
 - Summer/winter schools
 - Webinars
 - Online training modules
 - Other (specify):
- Q10 Do you have a training strategy?
- yes
 - no
- If yes, is it revised on a yearly basis or differently?
- Q11 If yes to question 10, who is the person responsible for the development/upgrade of the training strategy and who is responsible for its delivery (e.g. Director General, Training Officer etc.)?
- Q12 Is your research infrastructure involved in the delivery of formal university training courses, e.g. by providing access to research facilities for the purpose of delivering university courses?
- Q13 If yes to question 12, is this based on formal agreements between the research infrastructure and the university?
- If not, is this currently being planned?
- Q14 Does your research infrastructure have a special access request procedure for PhD students?
- Q15 Does your research infrastructure provide funding for PhD studentships?
- Q16 Does your research infrastructure have a website/webpage dedicated to training?
- Q17 In your experience, is the helpdesk/contact form/contact person for training fundamental to improving these activities?
- Q18 How many participants attend your training events (per event/ or yearly)?
- Q19 Does your research infrastructure adopt KPIs to monitor the training activities?
- If yes, which KPIs? and what are the tools used for?
- Q20 Do you have suggestions or comments to share with us?

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5 Sitography

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